

Election of Indonesian Presidential Candidates: A Sociological Review

Bado Riyono

University of Indraprasta PGRI

Corresponding Author: Bado Riyono bado.riyono79@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Election, president, sosiology

Received : 18, September

Revised : 10, October

Accepted: 15, November

©2023 Bado Riyono: This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](#).

ABSTRACT

The presidential election is a competition for power in a constitutional manner. Elections every 5 years are a hope for better. The public chose to hope that the president could improve the situation for the better. This research uses qualitative methods with a sociological approach. Respondents were 6 candidates for election in 2024. The research results show that people tend to vote based on options that can increase their confidence through the issues presented by the candidate. It can be based on ethnicity, religion, friends or other things that can inspire voter confidence.

INTRODUCTION

The President in Indonesia is elected directly by the people. In the General Election (Pemilu) in Indonesia, the principle of LUBER JURDIL is adhered to, namely direct, general, free, secret, honest and fair. Another interesting thing about the 2024 election is the importance of youth voting. Due to the large demographic structure, youth is one of the most important issues in elections (Sitorus, M. S., & Sitorus, 2023). With the attractive character and perspective of young people, they have their own preferences regarding the character of a president in 2024. According to young people, the ideal character to become a presidential candidate is a leader who has 3 attitudes, including: First, has high innovation, deep innovation. culture, culture, and also policies that will later be implemented during his reign. The second, namely an intelligent leader who understands all the problems in Indonesia as a whole and can take solutions with steps that have a good impact on all elements of society. The third, become an ideal leader It is necessary to have a strong grip, in the form of research and data obtained. It is hoped that the future presidential candidate will change or improve the systematics of a more advanced Indonesian government. Therefore, it is hoped that whoever will be elected president will be a leader who is responsible, honest, trustworthy, Consistent and firm in making decisions.

Elections are an embodiment of the human rights of Indonesian citizens by guaranteeing the right of every Indonesian citizen to express their political aspirations through existing political party channels in accordance with applicable legal provisions (Wahyudy, et al, 2021). A good election is an election that meets the principles in organizing elections, namely in accordance with Article 2 of Law Number 15 of 2011 concerning General Election Organizers, namely independence, honesty, fairness, legal certainty, orderliness, public interest, openness, proportionality, professionalism, accountability, efficiency and effectiveness.

Indonesia will soon hold a presidential election on February 14 2024. The 2024 election is an important moment to increase public political awareness and increase political participation. As students who understand their rights and obligations, it is appropriate for students to participate in voicing their thoughts regarding the upcoming electoral system and actively contribute to the implementation of the 2024 elections, remembering that Indonesia's future is in the hands of the people and should be fought for by the people. More than 204,807,222 domestic voters and 1.75 million Indonesian diaspora around the world will go to the polls on February 14 2024 to elect the next president and vice president. This gives its own color to the political atmosphere in Indonesia. The candidates who will compete are Prabowo Subianto, Anies Baswedan and Ganjar Pronowo.

Indonesian society, which consists of various groups and tribes, has the right to vote and determine their political rights in the context of the continuity of democracy. Society seems to be divided, between husband and wife, co-workers, village friends and so on. People have their own opinions and hopes, this is the dynamic of people's lives today.

People have their own opinions and beliefs. When they choose to be different, this can give rise to potential conflict within society itself (Sutopo, 2021). The issues raised by the presidential candidates are very diverse, including the lack of comprehensive absorption of people's aspirations and participation from the lower levels. Another issue is the tendency of increasingly widening social and economic gaps in society, especially small communities which are always left in an uncertain economic situation. And this can be seen when the government increases the economic burden on society in general, which triggers problems that affect the economic life of society (Mutiarasari, 2018). For example, currently, the government is increasing fuel prices on the grounds that this is due to the increase in world oil prices.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Presidential election

The meaning of General Elections, among other things, is to provide certainty regarding the constitutional transfer of leadership and power (transfer of Leader and Power) to produce legitimate leaders; General elections are a manifestation of the fundamental implementation of popular sovereignty in democratic countries; General Elections are intended as a formal vehicle for shaping state and social formation towards a better order; can be a filter for people's beliefs in political parties that are in people's minds. Meanwhile, according to Syamsudin Haris, General Elections are an institution as well as a political practice that allows the formation of a representative government. Meanwhile, according to A.S. Hikam, General Elections are an institution and at the same time a political practice that has 2 (two) dimensions, which from the outside appear to be at odds with each other.

In the first dimension, General Elections are generally understood as a means for realizing people's sovereignty and a means of articulating the interests of citizens to realize their representatives. Meanwhile, in the second dimension, the General Election is a means of providing and strengthening the government's political legitimacy, so that its existence, policies and programs can be realized more easily and have strong sanctions ties. The importance of holding General Elections is basically to implement people's sovereignty; elect people's representatives; convince or at least renew the agreement of the citizens; influencing citizen behavior; and educating rulers to increasingly rely on consent from the people rather than coercion to maintain their legitimacy. Some time ago the Constitutional Court (MK) granted the request of Effendi Gazali and his friends regarding elections being held simultaneously, both legislative member elections (Pileg) and Presidential Elections (Pilpres).

However, the Constitutional Court stated that this decision would only come into effect for the 2019 elections and beyond. The Constitutional Court considers that the 2014 election process is currently underway, so there are concerns that it will disrupt the ongoing election if it is carried out immediately. Pemilihan Presiden

Sociological Review

The sociological approach is an approach or method in which the discussion of an object is based on the society in the discussion. Based on the development of contemporary science, this science is used as a method for understanding and studying religion. The sociological approach is an approach that is linked to social theories, especially family sociology. It could be said that the object of study in sociology is human life, the process of interaction in society, and the products of human interaction in that society. The object of study of sociology focuses on structures in social groups, organizations and society, as well as the way people interact within these structures. According to Hadi (2006), the sociological approach basically explains that social characteristics and social groupings have quite a significant influence in determining voter behavior.

METHODOLOGY

The method used is a qualitative method. This research uses a sociological approach with four influencing factors, namely the influence of ethnicity and religion, in determining voting behavior. Data was taken through interviews, documentation and searching for news stories about the 2024 presidential candidate election. Respondents were prospective voters in 2024. A total of 6 people were sampled. Research locations in East Jakarta and South Jakarta. The research was carried out from August to November 2023.

Research stages include:

Figure 1. Research's step

The data stage starts from collecting data with interviews and documentation as well as searching for news about the presidential election. The activity continues with data reduction and data presentation, and ends with drawing conclusions and verification.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The community as the holder of voting rights is a diverse group of individuals who have their own opinions and choices in choosing the president. The characteristics of society can be divided into 3 groups, namely lower, middle and upper levels of society. Lower society has a basic instinct for thinking that is different from other levels. Lower level communities whose basic needs have not yet been met are very vulnerable to money politics and the lure of irrational programs (Badoh, I. Z. F., & Dahlan, 2010).

Middle and upper level society is more likely to think about how the presidential candidate's program can be implemented and overcome all the

problems of society itself. The upper level tends to use material power to influence other people.

According to the results of interviews with respondents, the respondents' choice of presidential candidate was based on 3 options, namely:

1. Choose based on the work program offered by the presidential candidate.
2. Choose based on negative or positive sentiments developing in society which are directly and indirectly related to the presidential candidate in question.
3. Choose on personal grounds and the relationship between the individual characteristics of the presidential candidate.

The presidential election is getting closer and voters continue to observe and process data, so that it can be used as a consideration and basis for choosing. Meanwhile, the process closest to voter behavior is the campaign before the election and events reported by the mass media (Pasaribu. et al, 2022). Each element in this process will influence voter behavior, although the focus of the Michigan Group study is party identification and developing political issues and candidates, and not their social or cultural background.

Figure 1. Candidate of President 2024

The 3 prospective candidates have the same right to be elected by the public. However, only 1 candidate will win the election. According to respondents from several ethnicities, they tend to be chosen based on ethnicity, for example Mahfud MD who comes from Madura, so it is suspected that the Madurese people will choose this partner. Likewise with Gibran who comes from Central Java, Solo, as well as Anies Baswdan who comes from Arab descent. In terms of religion, this is also the case, during the presidential election 5 years ago, KH Maruf Amin, a charismatic cleric, was able to send a message that religion is also an attraction for voters.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The presidential election in 2024 is a phenomenon that cannot be separated from society itself. People will choose according to what they have in mind. However, critical thinking is needed so that people are not deceived by the programs that will be offered. The programs offered will be forgotten and this will lead to lasting disappointment. Society is dynamic. They easily change according to many factors, starting from ethnicity, religion, friends and so on. Quality elections must also be created by quality communities.

REFERENCES

- Badoh, I. Z. F., & Dahlan, A. (2010). *Korupsi Pemilu di Indonesia*. Indonesia Corruption Watch.
- Hikam, M. A. (2000). *Islam, demokratisasi, dan pemberdayaan civil society*. Erlangga.
- Pasaribu, D., Fadiyah, D., Hakim, N. A. T. U., Fadillah, S., & Anom, A. (2022). PERILAKU PEMILIH (VOTING BEHAVIOUR) FORUM BETAWI REMPUG (FBR) DALAM PEMILU PRESIDEN INDONESIA 2019. *Madani Jurnal Politik dan Sosial Kemasyarakatan*, 14(02), 337-352.
- Sitorus, M. S., & Sitorus, S. H. (2023). Partisipasi Generasi Z dalam Menggunakan Hak Pilih pada Pemilihan Umum 2024 di SMK Taruna Pekanbaru. *EDU SOCIETY: JURNAL PENDIDIKAN, ILMU SOSIAL DAN PENGABDIAN KEPADA MASYARAKAT*, 3(2), 969-976.
- Sutopo, U. (2021). TOLERANSI BERAGAMA (Toleransi Masyarakat Muslim dan Budha di Dusun Sodong Perspektif Islam). *Al-Syakhsyiyah: Journal of Law & Family Studies*, 3(2), 48-82.
- Syamsuddin, A. B., & Ag, S. (2016). *Pengantar Sosiologi Dakwah*. Kencana.
- Mutiarasari, A. (2018). Peran entrepreneur meningkatkan pertumbuhan ekonomi dan mengurangi tingkat pengangguran. *Dinar: Jurnal Prodi Ekonomi Syariah*, 1(2), 51-75.
- Wahyudy, F. I., Sumadinata, W. S., & Agustino, L. (2021). Strategi Partai Solidaritas Indonesia Dalam Memenangkan Suara Pemilih Minoritas Pada Pemilihan Umum Legislatif Tahun 2019. *Jurnal Civic Hukum*, 6(1)